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Insights into individual migration decisions at the beginning of vocational training – The roles of perceived market demands and individual desires

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Abstract

Learning mobility and other international experiences are regarded as highly important in the (European) labour market. A number of support programmes and campaigns aim at fostering international exchange, a considerable part in the field of vocational education and training. Transnational mobility at the stage of initial vocational training has however hardly been researched yet. The author focuses on this research gap by analysing migration decisions of Polish trainees in Germany via a cross-sectoral analysis of individual partially structured interviews. First findings on two key aspects, namely perceived market demands and individual desires, are discussed in the paper.

Keywords

migration decision; vocational education and training; interview study; poland; germany

1 Topic and design of the research project

Although learning mobility is politically enforced by national and EU-programmes (BMBF, 2017), only a small number of young people chooses to go abroad for the whole period or part of their vocational training (e.g. Körbel, 2011, p. 18; Kalisch, 2012, p. 225). The dissertation project this paper is based on focuses on young people from Poland starting their apprenticeship in the northeast of Germany. It investigates two key aspects that have hardly been explored so far: individual motivation and central challenges (Thurnherr, 2015; Bohlinger, 2013, p. 121). The former concentrates on the influences that initiate, foster or inhibit the individual plan to take up a vocational training in another country. The latter pays particular attention to the various challenges young people who are willing to pursue this aim face, as the barrier to actually implement the plan is very high. This applies in particular to those with limited support from their social environment (Ulrich, Ehrental & Häfner, 2006, pp. 102-103).

The decision to go abroad for vocational training is neither exclusively a career choice decision nor exclusively a migration decision (Thurnherr, 2015). Acknowledging this, the dissertation project is based on both theories and findings on migration as well as career choice. These have been taken into consideration in the development of the research instrument. Individual partially structured face-to-face interviews with narrative-generating questions are being conducted. The target group includes Polish trainees who have started vocational training in the federal states of Mecklenburg-West Pomerania and Brandenburg. The survey period is set at the beginning of their apprenticeship. The interviews are being interpreted with the help of content analysis with a detailed analysis of the individual case and a cross-sectoral analysis.

Nine interviews with the duration of approximately two and a half hours each have been conducted so far and, thus, provide the basis for the analysis presented in this paper. The sample includes both apprentices in dual training occupations (5) and school-based vocational training occupations highly oriented on the dual system (4).

2 Key aspects within the migration decision

This paper focuses on the individual motivation for starting a vocational training in Germany. As stated above, research results on this learning mobility are sparse, so there is a need to include other research findings. Studies on short-term mobility within educational programmes have found a number of correlations between particular, mostly socio-economic, characteristics and the willingness to move. Concerning the individual reasons to go abroad, there are only a few studies with limited significance, especially focusing on young Spaniards coming to Germany for vocational training. According to these findings, the decision is largely connected to the economic crisis in the country of origin (Clement & Koch, 2014; Grünert & Wiener, 2016).

According to the definitions of the United Nations (1998, pp. 9-10) and the European Statistical Office (2016), long-term mobility can be understood as migration, as it usually leads to a transnational change of usual residence for the duration of more than one year. Reasons for migration include cultural, political, economic, religious, demographic, ecological, ethnic and social causes – external constraints, such as those connected to the labour market, are frequently mentioned (Han, 2010, pp. 5-17; Haug, 2013; Kalter, 2000; Lehmann, 2008). This is mirrored in the increasing importance of geographical mobility in the labour market (Friedel, Otto & Dalbert, 2003, pp. 4-5). In the case of long-term mobility there is an added positive connotation of the (alleged) development of abilities and attitudes initiated by staying abroad, e.g. independence, intercultural competence or tolerance of ambiguity. Such aspects can increase young people's willingness to accomplish their vocational training in a foreign country – be it as the first step to an international career or to increase chances on the labour market in the country of origin.

The individuals' personal wishes detached from external constraints are rarely addressed as central causes for transnational migration. However, such influences are expected to be of great impact for this particular migration decision. Going abroad is often advocated as an instrument to achieve personal development and desired by many young people who are curious to explore the world outside their home country (e.g. Grünert & Wiener, 2016, p. 28). Leaving the country of origin can thus be an instrument to pursue individual desires, interests and goals, e.g. experiencing an adventure, getting to know a different culture or improving language skills.

Accordingly, the question leading the analysis is: To what extent is the migration decision of Polish trainees in north-eastern Germany driven by (1) perceived market demands and (2) individual desires?

3 First findings on perceived market demands and individual desires

The interviews have been transcribed and processed in the program MAXQDA. Parallel to further data collection the cross-sectoral content analysis has been initiated. The categories derived from the interview guideline were supplemented by inductive categories based on the material. The first exemplary insights into the data with regard to the two dimensions of "perceived market demands" and "individual desires" are presented, which due to the ongoing analysis are of preliminary character and will be further analysed in the course of the project.

Table 1 Categories assigned to the dimensions in focus

Perceived market demands	Individual desires
1. Economic pressure in Poland	1. Experiencing something new
2. Educational programme in Poland unaffordable	2. Personal attachment to Germany
3. Better career prospects	3. Learning the German language
3 a. Professional future in general	
3 b. Salary Level	
3 c. Work-life balance	

3.1 Perceived market demands

Aspects that can be assigned to the dimension of perceived market demands include the problematic financial situation in the country of origin. This refers to the cost of living in general as well as to unaffordable educational programmes, as the following example shows:

Also vorher habe ich in Stettin überprüft, ob ich zum Beispiel Pflege- Kranke- Krankenpflegerin werden kann, aber dazu muss man Studium machen und das ist das große Unterschied zwischen Deutschland und Polen [...], drei Jahre und ohne Geld und das ist auch ein... Das ist immer Frage des Geldes. (Krystyna)

Krystyna tells about her initial idea to start a course of study in the field of health care in Poland, which would have been the only option to become a nurse in her home country. Financial reasons prevented this, as she would not have been able to earn money during the qualification process.

Another and very frequently expressed argument is that of better career prospects. These relate both to labour market opportunities after the completion of training and to conditions of employment. Both are assessed as significantly better in Germany and appear to be an important reason for respondents in their migration decision. Some of the interviewees clearly associate the training with a better professional future in general:

In Polen ist kei- nicht gute Zukunft, aber in Deutschland ist besser. Ist richtig gute Zukunft, besser als Polen. (Kacper)
Also nee, ich sag, ich glaube, hier wenn man hier eine Ausbildung macht, stehen bisschen mehr Türen offen. (Maria)

Kacper directly compares what he perceives as his possible professional future in the two countries and, without further explanation, claims a better one for himself in Germany. Maria, too, is convinced that there are 'more open doors to her' after a vocational training in Germany.

The expected better career prospects also include a higher salary. The interviewees describe that they already earn more money during the training in Germany than they would (or in fact have) as a trained professional in Poland. In conjunction with comparatively high costs of living in Poland, local salaries are considered insufficient:

Ich weiß nicht, wie die Menschen hier in Danzig leben, wenn sie haben normale Arbeit als Verkäuferin oder Sekretärin oder so weiter oder als Krankenschwester. Es ist unmöglich eine Arbeitsstelle mit den Kindern und so weiter und die Wohnung und Rechnungen alles das zu schaffen, nee ich weiß nicht. (Monika)

Monika expresses her doubts on how people with ‘regular jobs’ like sales assistants, secretaries or nurses can afford a living in her Polish home city. With regard to salary expectations, some of the respondents weighed up a course of study in Poland against the vocational training in Germany. This comparison between the two countries also applies to the prospective work-life balance:

*Wie schwer es ist, in Polen überhaupt das alles irgendwie als alleinige Mama hinkriegen. Weil entweder man geht arbeiten, oder man bleibt zu Hause, aber wenn man zu Hause bleibt, äh ja... Es war ziemlich schwer [...]. Hier ist viel, viel besser, sag ich, als in Polen. Einfacher so. Weil bei uns ist es nicht so einfach, dass man, keine Ahnung, so zu Hause bleiben kann und Geld kriegt. (Maria)
Und in Deutschland, Menschen haben Zeit für Ausruhen, ja? Wir arbeiten ganze Tag, ganze Tag, eine Arbeit, zweite, dritte, ne? Und in Deutschland, man hat eine Arbeit, ja? Und Freizeit, ja? Und Ausflug mit Fahrrad, mit Familien, ja, und ich find es besser. Nicht nur arbeiten. (Magdalena)*

The comparatively good situation for parents is emphasised by Maria, a single mother, who explains that a paid parental leave as in Germany does not exist in Poland, so one must either stay at home without financial support or go to work. Magdalena adds how important a balance between leisure and working time is for her. In Poland people would need to work multiple jobs whereas in Germany one employment is sufficient for a solid living, leaving time for rest and for the family.

3.2 Individual desires

The interviewees express partly diffuse, partly very specific motivations for wanting to live in Germany:

*Weil ich neugierig bin. Ich mag immer lernen, ich mag auch neue Länder kennen lernen und die Kultur. (Anna)
Also ich wollte immer in einem anderen Land wohnen. Also für mich ist interessant wie andere Leute leben und so weiter. (Krystyna)*

Some, like Anna, express curiosity about getting to know other countries and their cultures. Krystyna says she has always wanted to live abroad and get to know other ways of life. This interest is not directly linked to Germany, it is rather linked to a general interest in experiencing something new. Some interviewees express their long-standing personal attachment to Germany, however:

(Lacht) Keine Ahnung, ich weiß nicht, aber ich will nicht in Polen. Das ist... Ich war immer in... mit Deutschland verbunden und das... ja, das kommt von Herz aus, ich weiß nicht wie kann das erzählen, aber ja, das ist was ich will machen. In Deutschland arbeiten, in Deutschland wohnen, ja. (Monika)

Due to family members working in Germany during her childhood, Monika had been visiting Germany regularly and developed a strong attachment to this neighbouring country (‘it comes from the heart’). Living and working in Germany is exactly what she wants to do. Learning the German language, too, is an individual desire connected to the training in Germany, although it usually is not described as one of the main motives.

4 Conclusion and subsequent questions

The trainees’ narrations refer to a direct or indirect comparison between the two countries, particularly with regard to financial aspects and other labour-related matters. For many interviewees the vocational training in Germany is connected to a thirst for adventure, be it in terms of living abroad, getting to know another culture or improving the foreign language skills. In addition, Germany is particularly important for some of the young Poles because of

family members who have been living or live there, implying that the decision is directly linked to the country. In general, statements that can be assigned to the dimension of “perceived market demands” take up a much larger space in the interviews than those of “individual desires”. This might point to a greater impact of market demands for the migration decision of the trainees.

The analysis has provided a valuable insight into the significance of external constraints and internal needs for this particular migration decision. These and other expressed reasons for migrating will be examined in context by the means of individual case analyses. In this way, more profound conclusions are expected to be found regarding the role that these and other aspects play and how they are interconnected on an individual level.

The cross-sectional analysis itself will be extended by including more cases and by broadening the view to further dimensions. The interviews taken into consideration for this paper also point to motivations, apart from the above mentioned aspects, that lie in politics and social welfare and the quality of vocational training in Germany, as well as the kindness of its people and the geographical proximity to Poland.

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Biographical notes

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